

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

Organizational environment and the impact of cultural, social and personal factors on employee job satisfaction and performance

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World Journal of Advanced Research and Reviews, 2024, 21(01), 2871–2882

Publication history: Received on 12 December 2023; revised on 16 January 2024; accepted on 27 January 2024

Article DOI: <https://doi.org/10.30574/wjarr.2024.21.1.0262>

Abstract

Job satisfaction remains an important aspect of investigating performance, and its effect on productivity, organisational objectives, and societies as a whole and has been widely studied. This study aimed at investigating organisational environment and the impact of cultural, social, and personal factors of employee job satisfaction and studying the relationship between job satisfaction and performance in organisation while exploring the interrelationships of the antecedent's groups. The study confirms the dual direction of connection that consists of a cycle of cause-and-effect relationship between job satisfaction and performance and investigates the mediating factors. The study encourages supervisors and managers to reflect on their tacit method of handling workers and exploring ways to employ explicit methods and support work environment that is more conducive and unbiased. The study emphasizes the importance of considering job satisfaction and performance relationship holistically by addressing the cultural, social, and personal problems to improve employee performance.

Keywords: Organization; Environment; Cultural; Social; Personal; Satisfaction

1. Introduction

Organisations both in the private and the public sector, national and international, rely upon their employees for maximum production which will in turn result in efficiency. In the past, organisations concentrated on cost reduction approach and boosting of sales, however, research and practice in recent years demonstrated that one of the important aspects of high productivity is workers and how they are handled. According to Hoverstadt and Bowling (2002), a manager's ability to handle issues or organisation effectively is in direct proportion to the accuracy and importance of the models they are utilizing to understand it. In most cases, managers rely upon the tacit models that they have designed themselves to deal with worker's management without explicit formulation. This is mostly true for supervisory teams which have managed in the same organisation or sector for many years. In situations like these, the manager's tacit models can appropriately suggest assurance, providing the supervisory team with reasonable grounds for managing with the kind of daily issues that obviously disturbed their organisation. However, implementing the tacit models undeniably has many possible drawbacks as they can hide big differences in belief amongst managers and which can occasionally fail to support reasonable management on new issues. Tacit model is not available as a text, it consists of insubstantial factors established in individual beliefs, experiences, and values (Pan and Scarbrough, 1999).

Tacit models can also limit the eagerness and capability to deal and initiate with radical change as opposed to progressive change. The tacit models also emphasize employees' strengths without encouraging their weaknesses. Although, tacit model represents plentiful value to the organisation, by its nature, it is far more demanding and at times complicated to diffuse and overcome (Koulopoulos and Frappolo, 1999; Nonaka, 1994). Davenport and Prusak (1998) demonstrate the complexity associated with taking the tacit model in their instance of an effort to transfer the expertise

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of the world best aerial picture specialist into a skilful system by a computer expert. The skillful system was disastrous. As workplaces become bigger and more challenging, therefore there is a need to make use of explicit formal models that leaders can apply to share their experience and to communicate about the difficulty, tend to increase. Explicit knowledge entails accurate statements about matters such as technical information, tool characteristics and material properties (Koskinen et al, 2003). Organisation operating in rapid changing environments also need to utilize the explicit formal models for the intention of satisfying their employee and boosting their productivity.

Job satisfaction is a complex phenomenon since it arises from the worker evaluation of numerous job dimensions created each day (Kinicki et al., 2002). Furthermore, job satisfaction is not solely based on the degree to which the job itself offers the employee with satisfaction connected to a particular job characteristic but also on the degree to which the job characteristic is relevant to employee (Locke, 1969). Job satisfaction is a personal construct since it is a personal attitude centered on personal experience, which differentiate it from organisational environment experienced by an average individual or a combined attitude of organisation employees towards their jobs (Schneider, Erhart, and Macey 2011).

Job performance on the other hand, is described as the behavior that achieves results (Armstrong and Taylor, 2014). Overall organisational performance depends on the effective and efficient performance of its employees in the organisation. Therefore, almost all organisations place a considerable dependence on their employees' performance to attain high results in the organisation. Employee effort is a significant factor that determines their performance in the organisation. When employees are satisfied with the job that they do, they will be motivated and put in a greater effort to achieve a better result, and which will now increase the total performance of the organisation. In other words, a satisfied employee with commitment and effort is important for the success of the organisation. Knowing the job performance for everyone is important as the organisational decisions are centered on each employee's performance leading to organisational success (Sonnetag, Volmer and Spachala, 2008). Theoretically, various mechanisms have been accounted for to try to clarify why happy employees carry out their work better (Bakker and Demerouti, 2008). For instance, positive feelings improve employees through action performances, Therefore, increasing individual resources (Fredrickson, 2013). Furthermore, engaged employees are healthier, which means they can put more effort and energy into their assigned work. Job satisfaction is among the factors that impact the development of work performance (Kappagoda, 2012).

Even though job satisfaction and its impact on performance have been researched for decades, organisations still struggle to address and raise job satisfaction in a consistent fashion and factors surrounding the key relationship vary from research to research. Both performance and job satisfaction have their own determinants and factors and some of these factors are personal, cultural, social, and environmental factors (Gupta et al., 2012). The emerging literature increasingly points to shift of attention from personal factors to socio-cultural factors which are critical for employees to maintain performance and commitment to the organisation. Thus, this paper adds to existing studies by further examining personal, social, and cultural factors and their interplay in the job satisfaction and job performance correlation.

2. Literature review and the theoretical framework and hypotheses

Several studies have tried to capture the manner individuals experience and respond to the work that they do ever since the beginning of Organisational Psychology and ever since Behavior become a discipline. Within the domain of job attitudes, job satisfaction has been the one subject that is mostly researched about (Judge et al., 2017). The significance of job satisfaction has been showed in much research, which have discovered that job satisfaction is connected to range of organisationally and individually behaviors including turnover, absenteeism, work performance, counter-production work behavior (CWB), organisational citizenship behavior (OCB) and organisational cost-effectiveness (Judge and Kammeyer-Mueller, 2012). In organisational perspective, good job satisfaction can result to enhanced performance of the employees which increases the productivity of the organisation (Smith et al., 2020). Individual satisfaction is widely considered as a factor of employee productivity and retention. It is assumed that the behavior which enables an organisation to succeed is much more likely to occur when individuals feel committed to the organisation and are very motivated and when the obtain a high level of satisfaction (Paais and Pattiruhu, 2020). According to research, the major factors influencing the satisfaction of job are teamwork, job challenge, career opportunities and job influence (Riyadi, 2020).

According to Skibba (2002), the fundamental concept of this reciprocal ideal is that if the satisfaction is extrinsic, then it leads to performance, and the performance leads to satisfaction, however if the satisfaction is intrinsic, then the performance leads to satisfaction. In addition, the connection between job satisfaction and performance derived from social exchange model, in which job satisfaction is to be a gain by the workers to the organisation from which they obtain

their satisfaction. Physical and psychological benefits have significant effect on job satisfaction, employees should be rewarded and motivated to achieve job satisfaction, and which will eventually result to a positive impact on the effectiveness and efficiency of employees and therefore enhanced total performance (Indermun and Bayat, 2013).

The cultural factor is a crucial factor that impacts job satisfaction and performance because it defines the inner environment of the organisation in which the workers do their work and accomplish the need results (Schein 2004; Ashkanasy et al. 2001). Organisational culture can have a negative or positive impact on employee satisfaction and performance. Positive culture improved commitment of the employees (Yildirim et al., 2016). The social factor on the other hand is extremely important because job satisfaction relates to organisational attitudes such as connection with work colleague, supervision, or top management, working in group, decision making participation, informal relations, autonomy, and empowerment. An employee not participating in any of these factors is likely to be dissatisfied. According to Raza, Anjum and Zia, (2014), the social behavior of people influences their work. Personal factors of job satisfaction include age, gender, education, years of experience, occupation, role, or personal status. These factors are believed to have a big influence on an individual's job satisfaction. Previous studies have shown that job satisfaction could be designed by genetic components and life accomplishment (Schulz and Schultz, 2006). According to McCann (2002), several personal factors of job satisfaction such as age and gender affect the satisfaction of employees hugely. The nature of the connection between job satisfaction and social cultural values is such a difficult task. Browaeys and Price (2008), Deresky and Christopher (2011) explain how active leaders, and specifically those in worldwide corporations need to know about social cultural differences.

2.1. Theoretical Framework and Hypotheses

We present a theoretical framework (Figure 1) that predicts job satisfaction is more widely centered on the seminal work of earlier research. This piece of work builds on the work of Gupta et al. (2012) which found that satisfaction of job is influenced mainly by four variables. The cultural, social, personal, and environmental and organisational factors. This composition of factors was further backed by different authors such as Watson (2012) and Armstrong et al. (2014). This study further explores the nature of some of these group of factors such as cultural, social, and personal factors to find out and come to conclusion on what organisational management must do to resolve the barriers of these group of factors which hindered employee satisfaction and performance.

Figure 1 Theoretical framework: Job satisfaction, performance, and their related factors

The framework shows the common factors impacting job satisfaction and performance of employees in organisations. These factors are grouped into three parts such as cultural, social, and personal factors. The framework also shows double direction of the relationship and combines a cycle of cause-and-effect relationship. The line between the two variables indicates that the two variables have indirect influence on each other. Which means, job satisfaction leads to performance and performance leads to job satisfaction through mediating factors of cultural, social, and personal.

The cultural factor is a crucial factor that impacts job satisfaction and performance because it defines the inner environment of the organisation in which the workers do their work and accomplish the need results (Schein 2004; Ashkanasy et al. 2001). Cultural distance or differences can also affect business activity at numerous levels. For instance, at the national practice level, the recent global Covid-19 pandemic, and the USA-China trade war echo cultural disparities in how countries understand and respond to problems. At the industry, The China MNC has had to challenge a series of cultures such as Huawei, the China MNC giant, is tangled in political disagreement over delicate safety matters lessening from its partnership with Western technology businesses. At the supervisory level, international transformations amongst host nation subsidiaries and headquarters reveal MNC employees to numerous cultures, where diverse social beliefs and organisational cultures become familiar with, leading to threatening troubles to follow (Lee et al., 2019). These troubles result to cross-cultural doubt and mental distress that influence personal choices and dedication to the organisation (Ghemawat, 2017), generating identity worry between leaders (Kraimer et al., 2012). Through experience and exposure of numerous cultures, leaders and other experts become carriers of cultures, manipulating decisions, politics, favorites, their interactions with other and about decisions they make in their environments (Hoff and Stiglitz, 2016; Li and Van den Steen, 2021). Stephen and Stephen, (2016) explained that the differences in culture influence the attitude of employees that diverse cultures have different practices. A good organisational culture inspires individuals to perform their tasks with passion and drive. The more inspiring the organisational culture is, the greater the level of job commitment and job satisfaction. Organisational strong culture can fascinate talented employees and lower turnover rate (Kim et al., 2017). The above discussion to the first hypothesis.

H1: *Individual employees' cultural values significantly impact organizational values and goals, whereby the higher the shared beliefs, values, and goals, the higher level of satisfaction of the employee.*

The social factor on the other hand is extremely important because job satisfaction relates to organisational attitudes such as connection with work colleague, supervision, or top management, working in group, decision making participation, informal relations, autonomy, and empowerment. An employee not participating in any of these factors is likely to be dissatisfied. According to Raza, Anjum and Zia, (2014), the social behavior of people influences their work. Workplaces are made up of individuals, who are by nature social beings. As a result, these people come as one in a formal way and set up by the company structures (e.g., teamwork, company hierarchy), and in numerous circumstances, Individuals use informal techniques to meet other people like them (Byrne, 1971; Tsui and O'Reilly, 1989). Social identity theory emerges in 1970s from Tajfel's works to clarify why people show favorites for fellow teammates (Haslam and Ellemers, 2011; Haslam et al., 2014). For instance, basically by being classified into a group with another person, teammates show preferences towards fellow group colleagues and discriminate toward outside group colleagues (Ashforth and Mael, 1989). To clarify this phenomenon, social identity theory suggests that people who are in the same group identify with the outlining features and beliefs of that group (Tajfel and Turner, 1985). The above discussion leads to the second hypothesis.

H2: *Individual employees' social identity significantly increases organization's values, whereby the more employees' identity themselves, their role identity, and the more the organization encourages social cultural integration, the greater satisfaction is of the employees.*

Personal factors of job satisfaction include age, gender, education, years of experience, occupation, role, or personal status. These factors are believed to have a big influence on an individual's job satisfaction. Previous studies have shown that job satisfaction could be designed by genetic components and life accomplishment (Schulz & Schultz, 2006). Several personal factors of job satisfaction such as age and gender affect the satisfaction of employees hugely. The connection of age and gender thus relies on their expressions and bodily dimension. For instance, the production of employees who are between the age of 59 and above is stated to be lower than those who are between the age of 58 and below (Cheal, 2002). Therefore, one of the personal factors which is age negatively impacts the job satisfaction of employees as well. Gender variances in job satisfaction have engrossed consideration of numerous researchers; in the year 1990, Greenhaus, Parasuraman and Wormley, establish no substantial variances in gender but they justified these outcomes describing that the male employees have rewarding positions than the female employees. They indicated that female employee could be more satisfied when they have fewer challenging jobs due to their lesser expectation (Spector, 2012). Personal factors could also be connected to the employee's roles. An employee's role is believed to have a big influence on an individual's job satisfaction. People select a profession that is preferred by them while others end up in their work because of high pressure. Pressure can arise from the desire to make more money or a guardian defining or making decisions related to their career. When an individual himself selects his or her profession they will work with interest and be happy about what they do. motivation for the job results in developing a positive attitude (Omah and Obiekwe, 2019). The above discussion leads to the third hypothesis.

H3: *Individual employees' personal traits, and their capacity for acting as a significant contributor significantly increase their satisfaction with their organization.*

The current study will explore the practicality of the proposed theoretical model and high order hypotheses around these three groups of factors, building a steppingstone for future research studying the relationship between job satisfaction and performance more comprehensively.

3. Methods

3.1. Study Instruments and Measures

The study includes a set of processes, as well as pre-investigation for the questionnaire design, distribution of questionnaire, and statistical analysis. The questionnaire was centered on the HR management literature, as well as experimental work referenced. The design concentrated on the proposed model (Figure 1) by which the variables and measured were refined following interviews with several HRM managers and workers. We used three sets of measures, 1) cultural, 2) social, 3) personal. The analyses also involved a set of measures that enable subjects to express their commitment and satisfaction and assessment of their performance at the workplace. (The above used as dependent variables).

Instruments for data gathered and scale measures for all variables, using five-point Likert scale with the following scoring, 1=strongly disagree and 5 strongly agree. The data sets are treated data in the database. Using scales of turnover intentions, the dependent variable (Jex, 2002). Data measures of the other sets varied depending on the nature of the data. For example, demographics are identified by nominal values, experience by scale values, and countries by strings, such as 1 the UK, 2 for EU countries, and so on. We use taxonomy to cluster data in the database.

3.2. Data Collection

We repeatedly distributed questionnaires to the target population of employees who are currently employed in UK organisations, either small, medium, or large, either large multinational companies, institutions, or private companies. The response rate was 60% as 307 questionnaires were collected for the analysis. The proportion of male participants were higher than that of the female and the rate of their marital status was reasonably balanced. Education status indicates that a large proportion of the respondents have either a master's degree or a bachelor's, which shows that in general they have gained a university level education.

3.3. Data Screening

The data scales (from the survey) reliability was tested using composite factor reliability scores and Cronbach Alpha (Netemeyer, 2003). The Cronbach coefficient on average was 0.82. Average Variance Extracted (AVE) mostly attained above 0.80, which recommended some construct-related variances, as Hair et al. (2011) suggest. Even though an arbitrary rule-of-thumb generally uses < 4 as a cut off tolerance (Fox, 2001) the criterion attained for the Variance-Inflation Factor (VIF) > 0.20 . For model fit, the screening of all data variables diagnosed multi collinearity by applying a correlation matrix. In diagnosing the presence of heteroscedasticity White's $y = 0$ null hypothesis was used (Pindyck and Rubinfeld, 1998). To diagnose error variance, data variables not meeting the validity requirements for the analysis were omitted.

To address the problem of 'common method variance' as the result of systematic error variance (Ireland et al., 1987) if survey measurement might engender 'rater effects' or context effects' (Podsakoff et al., 2003). The survey design sought to reduce the biasing effects, which could connect to 'rater bias's or rater effect (Podsakoff et al. 2003). The former is restrained by the survey design, which concentrates on current employees either locally or internationally. Sample population had a wide range of experience and across countries. Some consideration given to the differences between demographics experience among expatriates could also have improved data quality through comparative analyses. We sought to lower the 'systematic error variance' (Ireland et al., 1987). The error can refer to differences drawn from perceptions without context. We restricted the chance of data bias by highlighting individual opinions relating to experience in different environments and conditions with which they participated.

3.4. Analytical Structures

We develop a set of analyses by which to assess the interrelation between social, cultural, and personal factors with employee perceived performance and their satisfaction and so forth. We seek to clarify whether it is social, cultural, and personal. Secondly, we assess by studying whether it has a positive or negative relationship with satisfaction, and if so,

why. In tackling these questions, we seek to clarify the significance of contextualised social personal factors. In numerous research, commitment and satisfaction intention are considered as dependent variables. We also included mediating and control variables, which differed, depending on the instant argument in the analysis.

3.5. Hypothesis Testing Procedures and Techniques

To test Hypothesis 1, (xx) satisfaction is examined in connection to a set of cultural variables, including cultural beliefs, cultural similarity, cultural fit, cultural intelligence and so forth, while satisfaction and xx is the dependent variable. The comparison made in allows the analysis to examine cultural impacts in relations to cultural characteristics and disparities among employees. The analysis used ordinary least squares (OLS) because they could take n observations that consist of: $(y_i, x_i) = 1$. Every observation involved a scalar response y_i and a vector of P predictors (or regression) x_i , this assisted an examination of not only the data effect of a particular variables but also the value impact on numerous scales (e.g., 1, compared with 4) or whether the significance was likely derived from higher or lower scales of data values. Using OLS, we sought squared vertical distances between the observed responses in the database and the responses predicted by the linear approximation.

Hypothesis 2 and Hypothesis 3 tests used linear model and incorporated several different statistical models such as analysis of ANOVA through t-test and f-test, ordinary linear regression. Particularly, we tested $y = xB + u$, where y was a matrix with sequence of multivariate measurements, x was a matrix that may be a design matrix, B is a matrix comprising parameters which are to be assessed and u was a matrix comprising errors or noise. In the planning towards building model, we also thought of linear regression, using stepwise, enter, and removal processes for creating model fit.

To summarize, we used correlation analysis, confirmatory analysis, and hierarchical regression analysis to forecast estimated values (probability and error residuals) achieved through first stage and second-stage analysis to enlighten the distribution, for the value to be rested on the dependent variable which were centered on multiple sets of data in d -dimensional structure (different matrices) of analysis. The difficult relationships lie in the examination and exploration of a database in d -dimensions. The analysis used statistical software SPSS26.0 for carrying out observations on coefficients and probability distributions.

4. Result

Using the Dependent Variable: The mean value of the 5-item measure of Satisfaction, the research developed the analysis of five models and obtained results, as presented in Table 1 and Table 2. First, results from Model 1 (Table 1) test showed there was a negative relationship between employee's cultural impact within the organization and employees' performance Results suggest that the employee's cultural negatively relates to his satisfaction if the individual employee does not feel he has the sense of belong within the organisation ($b = -0.144, SE = 0.043, p < 0.001$). But there is a positive relationship between the employee's happiness when he feels his organizational goals, values and beliefs are connected to his own interests and values, suggesting the importance.

Of shared objectives and goals between the employee and the employer ($b = 0.280, SE = 0.037, p < 0.001$). The results support the researcher's prediction presented earlier in the conceptual framework: *Hypothesis 1. Individual employees' cultural values significantly impact organizational values and goals, whereby the higher the shared beliefs, values, and goals, the higher level of satisfaction of the employee.*

Results from Model 2 test (in Table 1) suggest that the impact of social identity factors of employees on their satisfaction, whereby individual employees more identify themselves with the group (organization), and when the organisation promotes a sense of oneness on employee jobs and responsibilities, the more the employees induce positively satisfaction with their job and employer ($b = 0.11, SE = 0.044, p < 0.014$), and more the employees feel their duty and contributions to the team, and more they feel they are strongly tied to the organisation, and the higher level of satisfaction, given the linear distribution of the scale data on the regressors- the observed variables ($b = 0.16, SE = 0.038, p < 0.001$). The results support the prediction presented earlier in the conceptual framework: *Hypothesis 2. Individual employees' social identity significantly increases organization's values, whereby the more employees' identity themselves, their role identity, and the more the organization encourages social cultural integration, the greater satisfaction is of the employees.*

Results from Model 3 test (in Table 1) suggest that the impact of personal factors of employees on their organisation and their satisfaction, whereby there were 3-items in the measure of personal impacts significant. First, employees felt they were less satisfied, when they less perceived their work at keeping their job skills up-to date ($b = -0.81, SE = 0.032,$

$p < 0.012$), but secondly, they felt they were satisfied when they came up with creative solutions to new problems in my organisation ($b = 0.153, SE = 0.041, p < 0.001$), and thirdly, they felt they were satisfied when they participated regularly in work meetings ($b = 0.131, SE = 0.039, p < 0.001$). Results suggest that the employee's personal influences are the important and significant factor for organisation to grow and, in turn, their rewards, belongs, and satisfaction. The results support the prediction presented earlier in the conceptual framework: *Hypothesis 3. Individual employees' personal traits, and their capacity for acting as a significant contributor significantly increase their satisfaction with their organization.*

Table 1 Hypotheses Testing Results of Model 1-Model 3

	Model 1			Model 2			Model 3		
	Overall Mean Satisfaction			Overall Mean Satisfaction			Overall Mean Satisfaction		
Independent Var.	Beta	Std. Error	P-value	Beta	Std. Error	P-value	Beta	Std. Error	P-value
(Constant)	3.316	(0.192)	0.001	2.605	0.244	0.001	2.799	(0.245)	0.001
Cultural Factor 1	-0.009	(0.04)	0.816	-0.002	0.038	0.95	-0.012	(0.036)	0.735
Cultural factor 2	-0.045	(0.038)	0.234	-0.066	0.038	0.085	-0.045	0.038	0.231
Cultural factor 3	-0.033	(0.036)	0.355	-0.039	0.034	0.259	-0.068	0.033	0.042
Cultural factor 4	-0.144	(0.043)	0.001	-0.102	0.042	0.017	-0.068	0.042	0.104
Cultural factor 5	0.28	(0.037)	0.001	0.172	0.04	0.001	0.096	0.042	0.022
Social factor 1				-0.022	0.045	0.623	-0.036	0.043	0.402
Social identity				0.11	0.044	0.014	0.082	0.046	0.073
Social factor 3				0.056	0.05	0.261	0.069	0.048	0.152
Social factor 4				-0.031	0.032	0.325	-0.037	0.031	0.238
Social factor 5				0.16	0.038	0.001	0.115	0.038	0.003
Personal factor 1							-0.063	0.037	0.092
Personal factor 2							-0.081	0.032	0.012
Personal factor 3							-0.045	0.031	0.146
Personal factor 4							0.153	0.041	0.001
Personal factor 5							0.131	0.039	0.001
<i>Model fit</i>									
F-value	27.50			16.25			18.47		
R	0.57			0.632			0.632		
Adj. R ²	0.313			0.378			0.378		
Std. Error	0.541			0.513			0.513		
Significance	0.001			0001			.001		
<i>df</i>	308			303			288		

Results from Model 4 test (in Table 2) suggest that the mediation effect of social identity of employees on culture, social factors, and personal impact, whereby the study also observed the moderation effect of interaction items. The variable of social identity creates both positive and negative impacts on how employees fit into my organisation, perception of their values within their group or organisation, while their duty and contributions to the team by defining themselves who they are, taking on extra responsibilities, participating regularly in work meetings. More importantly, the interaction items of Culture influence* Social factor are positively related to social identity of employees ($b = 0.08, SE = 0.025, p < 0.002$) and Culture * Personal ($b = 0.272, SE = 0.022, p < 0.001$) are positively related to social identity, but

Social *Personal are natively related to the social identity ($b = -0.142, SE = 0.016, p < 0.001$). The results support the prediction presented earlier in the conceptual framework: *Hypothesis 3. Individual employees' personal traits, and their capacity for acting as a significant contributor significantly increase their satisfaction with their organization.*

Results from Model 5 test (in Table 2) suggest that the impact of employee performance on their satisfaction with their organisation and their jobs, whereby there were 3-items of the measure of performance significant, Results suggest that the positive relationship between employees' performance and their satisfaction under the conditions, when they feel they have confidence to carry out their dues ($b = 0.142, SE = 0.051, p < 0.006$), and when they feel they can be proud to say they work for their organisation and would recommend to friends, they raise their satisfaction levels with the organization ($b = 0.102, SE = 0.036, p < 0.005$), and when they feel they can make a commitment to my organisation, their satisfaction levels with the organization increase ($b = 0.255, SE = 0.031, p < 0.001$). The results support the prediction presented earlier in the conceptual framework: *Hypothesis 5. Individual employees' performance significantly relates to satisfaction of the employees, whereby the higher the employees' confidence, sense of citizenship, the higher level of satisfaction of the employees with their organization.*

Table 2 Hypotheses Testing Results of Model 4-Model 5: Moderation and Mediation effect.

	Model 3			Model 4		
	Mediation Social Identity			Overall Mean Satisfaction		
	Beta	Std. Error	P-value	Beta	Std. Error	P-value
(Constant)	0.172	(0.391)	[0.661]	1.392	0.254	[0.001]
Cultural Factor 1	0.238	(0.057)	[0.011]	-0.027	0.031	[0.383]
Cultural factor 2	0.207	(0.052)	0.011	-0.018	0.032	[0.589]
Cultural factor 3	0.208	0.066	0.002	-0.056	0.029	0.053
Cultural factor 4	-0.02	0.067	0.762	-0.053	0.036	0.137
Cultural factor 5	0.033	0.073	0.651	0.057	0.036	0.119
Social factor 1	0.172	0.391	0.661	-0.045	0.038	0.236
Social identity				0.076	0.039	0.054
Social factor 3	0.023	0.069	0.739	0.035	0.044	0.428
Social factor 4	0.045	0.078	0.56	-0.001	0.027	0.983
Social factor 5	0.155	0.049	0.002	0.087	0.033	0.008
Personal factor 1	0.135	0.06	0.025	-0.082	0.032	0.011
Personal factor 2	-0.196	0.058	0.001	-0.043	0.028	0.123
Personal factor 3	0.094	0.051	0.065	-0.053	0.027	0.048
Personal factor 4	0.12	0.049	0.016	0.076	0.036	0.034
Personal factor 5	-0.178	0.065	0.006	0.067	0.034	0.048
Performance 2				0.03	0.041	0.461
Performance 2				0.142	0.051	0.006
Performance 3				0.036	0.046	0.437
Performance 4				0.102	0.036	0.005
Performance 5				0.255	0.031	0.001
Culture * Social	0.08		[0.002]			
Culture * Personal	0.272	0.022	0.001			

Social *Personal	-0.142	0.016	0.001			
<i>Model fit</i>						
F-value	19.85			16.25		
R	0.712			0.690		
<i>Adj. R²</i>	0.482			0.476		
Std. Error	0.778			0.484		
Significance	0.001			0.001		
<i>df</i>	284			0.283		

5. Discussion

Factors impacting job satisfaction and performance are Cultural, Social, and personal factors (Armstrong et al., 2014). The cultural factor is an important factor that influence job satisfaction and performance because it describes the internal environment of the organisation in which the employees carry out their work and achieve the require outcomes (Schein 2004; Ashkanasy et al. 2001). The culture of an organisation can have a positive and negative influence on employee performance and satisfaction. Positive culture improved commitment of the employees (Yildirim et al., 2016). The more motivating the organisational culture is, the better the level of job satisfaction and job commitment. Organisational strong culture can attract brilliant employees and reduce turnover rate (Kim et al., 2017).

The social factors are equally very important as well because job satisfaction correlates to organisational attitudes such as relationship with workmates, supervisors, or top management, group work, decision making involvement, informal relationships, independence, and liberation. workers not contributing to any of these factors are likely to be disappointed. According to Social Information Processing Theory (SIPT), as social beings, people pay close interest to the actions and ideas of the group. Human creatures have driven us to depend on others for information which allows them to establish a full image of themselves (Festinger, 1954).

Personal factors of job satisfaction include age, gender, education, years of experience, occupation, role, or personal status. These factors are believed to have a big influence on an individual's job satisfaction. Personal factors could also be connected to the employee's roles. An employee's role is believed to have a big influence on an individual's job satisfaction. People select a profession that is preferred by them while others end up in their work because of high pressure. Pressure can arise from the desire to make more money or a guardian defining or making decisions related to their career. When an individual himself selects his or her profession they will work with interest and be happy about what they do. motivation for the job results in developing a positive attitude (Omah and Obiekwe, 2019).

Both performance and job satisfaction have their own determinants and factors and some of these factors are personal, cultural, social (Gupta et al., 2012). This research was conducted to guide initial model tests between groups of factors to carry out the real relationship between job satisfaction and job performance in high quality. Much secondary and primary data has been included to get an actual understanding of the study question and earlier research from several professionals within the same domain was also looked at. This study will enable future researchers to examine a set of critical issues in the dynamic social organisational environment. The research has also taken a step further to contribute knowledge for HRM in the changing organisational environment, particularly, cultural, social, and personal issues in connection with diverse workforce motivations.

6. Conclusion

Based on the results of this piece of study, it is suggested that managers consider job satisfaction holistically and study all sets of factors, creating a work atmosphere that is more conducive to enabling employees perform work effectively. Looking at the sets of factors explored in the model could affect job satisfaction and the performance of employees. Although explored widely the nature of managing the connected sets of factors remains a difficult task and more empirical research is required. Organisations need to enhance training and development systems that will improve the level of work performance and improve employees' different needs. Regular in-depth evaluations of satisfaction and performance should be employed to check the level of these important variables and set the corrective procedures. The study proposed a basis for exploring the sub-factors influencing job performance and satisfaction with more study of

the influence of cultural, social, and personal aspects, which should be tackled through future research and practice implementation assessments.

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